

Notes along the Silk Road: What Mineralogy Can Tell Us about Trust

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INTRODUCTION

In 2008 and 2012, I was lucky enough to volunteer for archaeological fieldwork at Mechet'-Mohyla (archaeologically known as the settlement of Kinski Vody) near Orikhiv in the Zaporizhzhia region of Ukraine. See Figure 1. Volunteering was primarily possible thanks to the openness of the NGO "New Archaeological School." Fieldwork supervisor Mykhailo Elnikov spoke emphatically about the northern branch of the Silk Road, which passed through the Zaporizhzhia region and gave rise to a dozen Golden Horde cities. Those cities experienced an era of cultural prosperity in the 13th and 14th centuries (Elnikov 2016; 2018a; 2018b; 2019; 2022). In the 14th century, the ancient settlement on the left bank of the Konka River could boast a population of about 20,000 people, as evidenced by archaeological research and the remains of several large buildings in the area. See Figure 2. I took part in the excavation of one of the structures (presumably a mosque) which sits on a 20x20 m foundation built of local stone and brick. The fact that the structure belongs to the Golden Horde epoch was indicated by many fragments of kashi mosaic tiles. Kashi ceramics emerged in Iran in the 11th-12th centuries as an imitation of expensive Chinese porcelain products and later became a special ceramic group. Such tiles were made of high-quality porcelain-like quartz mass and became widespread between the 12th and 17th centuries throughout Iran, Central Asia, Transcaucasia, and areas touched by the Golden Horde. The many colours and differently-shaped fragments of kashi were mounted on walls in fresh mortar following a clearly thought-out pattern: the so-called coat. At the site of Kinski Vody, some of the remnants of the coat ornaments can be partially reconstructed, evidencing the presence of a fascinating decoration. However, up until present, scholars have little (if any) knowledge of what the tiles paints were made of, what pigments were used for turquoise, blue, green, yellow or red glaze, and where such products might have been sourced.

Figure 1. A schematic map of the Silk Road showing larger urban nodes. Kinski Vody, the site under discussion, is shown at the top left. Image by Simon Radchenko, used here with permission.

With this question in mind, a research project was born. I am sincerely grateful to Professor Mykhailo Elnikov of Zaporizhzhia National University for providing the samples. Elnikov presented part of the results as an addendum to his detailed classification and analysis of kashi building ceramics from the Kinski Vody

settlement (Elnikov 2017). The results of the study were published in a small edited volume in Russian (Radchenko 2017). However, this research is still useful for a broader audience as a study of the application of mineralogical research methods in archaeology. This is doubly important as the work was done in unoccupied Crimea in the Crimean branch of the Ukrainian State Geological Exploration Institute (Simferopol). This was where my parents – Igor Palkin and Olena Palkina worked, and which has now been completely destroyed. I am very grateful to them and other employees of the Institute for the opportunity to conduct these studies.

Fig. 2. Mausoleum in Kinski Vody. Retrieved on 31.04.2024 from "Seven mosques in Zaporizhyya region. Islam v Ukraini. URL: <https://islam.in.ua/ua/istoriya/sim-mechetey-na-zaporizhzi-0>

Due to the full-scale Russian invasion which has been going on for more than two years now, the territory of the monument has been subjected to continuous shelling and destruction. It is unclear whether we will ever be able to supplement the existing information by returning to the study of the settlement and its buildings. This provides even greater motivation to present this study to a wider range of readers.

Materials and methods

We studied mosaic fragments from the ornamentation of the public building of the Kinski Vody settlement, excavated in the summer of 2012. The mosaic pieces have the same quartz base and were covered with a coloured layer made of glaze. See Figure 3.

Figure 3. Fragments of the mosaic under study in situ. Photo by Anna Radchenko.

Elnikov (2017) points out that the basis of kashi (and the majority of the building ceramics at the Kinski Vody settlement belong to friable kasha), which is typical of other Golden Horde centers. Referring to the Koval, Elnikov writes that kashi is mostly quartz sand ground into powder, with the possible addition of fluxes (a small amount of white clay, lime) and mixed with an aqueous solution of glue of animal or vegetable origin and fused at a temperature of 900–1000°C.

The chemical compound of the kashi mosaics from the Kinski Vody site is mainly quartz (river alluvial sand) with a high content of silica (SiO_2) in the range of 90.42–93.83 %, with additions of clay – 0.92–2.92 % and lime – 4.14–6.48 %. There is an insignificant amount of micro admixtures (total mass about 2–2.33 %) of rock-forming minerals in the composition: quartz, clay, and sometimes potassium feldspar (Al_2O_3 , Fe_2O_3 ,

MgO). Kashi bricks from Kinski Vody featured larger sand grains than mosaic tiles, with quartz and magnetite grains up to 1 mm in size (Elnikov 2017). The colour of the Kinski Vody kashi also varies slightly (dirty-white, yellowish-gray, light gray). According to Koval (2010), there is no connection between the colour of kashi and the place of its production: those typical of the Golden Horde centers of the Volga region in the 14th century are also found in 14th–15th century structures from Iran, Central Asia and Syria.

The coloured layer of the Kinski Vody mosaic fragments mainly consists of a white plum solid substrate base (slipware) with an upper coloured coating of white, blue (with different colour intensity), green, turquoise (both bright and light), yellow and red. Fragments of red and yellow colours have an easily-scratched matte surface, while others are shiny and dense. The yellow fragments feature a slightly different substrate, (white-blue instead of blue colouring and greater homogeneity). The green fragments are covered with a thin transparent layer of iridescent glass, reminiscent of chandelier glass.

The mineral, granulometric and chemical composition of the fragments – their base, substrate, and colour layer – were studied through photoluminescence, spectroscopic and spectral analyses. The use of spectroscopy proved to be uninformative. Therefore, only the data of the photoluminescence and spectral analyses are discussed below.

Results

Microscopic description and mineral composition (binocular, 25× magnification). The composition of the samples is briefly characterized in Table 1. Their microscopic description is given below.

Blue fragment (No. 5). The colored layer is 0.2 mm thick. Half of it is covered with the white substrate (base), other half – with the colored coating. The colored layer is blue, the glass surface is flat, covered with cracks. Blue glass breaks into irregular pieces (up to 5 mm) when crushed. There are almost no inclusions in the blue coating. The mass is smooth and dense. There are air bubbles and undermelted quartz fragments (grains *with* melted edges) under the surface, and cracks diverge from them. Air bubbles are more abundant in the lower part of the coating, where dusty dark particles (probably magnetite) also can be seen. The color of the glass changes from light blue, brightens and becomes almost white closer to the quartz fragments.

Beneath the glass there is a white substrate consisting of fused quartz grains, granularly homogeneous, white and transparent. Under physical impact the substrate breaks into the grains of natural size — *about* 1 mm or less, sometimes up to 0.2 mm. Quartz grains from the substrate, as well as those from the fragments base, are taken from river alluvium, as evidenced by the high degree of fossilization. There are no sharp fragments – the glass pieces are slightly melted (probably, quartz grains were additionally pulverized). A small amount of feldspar included in the substrate is represented by weakly calcined grains.

The substrate is applied to a porous yellowish substance – the base of the mosaic, consisting of quartz, small crystals of gypsum and dust, single grains of feldspar and magnetite. The base does not contain impurities of carbonate material. It is made from the mentioned alluvial river sediments, widely presented in Ukraine. Therefore, it is impossible to specifically define the place of their extraction on the basis of mineral composition only.

Turquoise bright fragment (No. 1). The total thickness of the colored layer is 0.2 mm, and the white base is less than half. The rest is as in sample No. 5.

Turquoise light fragment (No. 1a). The colored layer is 0.3–0.5 mm thick, the white base accounts for more than half. The rest is as in No. 5, except for the cracks are absent on the glass surface.

Quartz fragments in fragments No. 1 and 1a are less pelletized and larger than in No. 5. There are more broken grains 0.1–0.5 mm in size. It seems that for tile type No. 5, the sand was sifted more carefully, and the fraction with smaller grain size was taken.

The glass is mainly represented by sparsely melted shards ranging from 0.1 to 0.5 mm.

Gypsum is acute-angled and is present as dust or in clusters. Small crystals of gypsum were formed in the process of heating the mass.

Same as the blue coating, the turquoise one splits upon physical impact into large (up to 5 mm) irregularly shaped fragments. The surfaces of the fragments are shiny, translucent, with air bubbles, without other inclusions.

White fragment (No. 3). The colored layer is 0.5 mm thick, the white substrate accounts for about 0.1 mm. The rest is as in sample No. 5. However, there are almost no cracks on the glass surface. There are inclusions of smoky quartz and pieces of blue and turquoise glass. Quartz is coarse-grained, with inclusions, pelletized. Fragments are 1–1.5 mm in size, the main mass consists of 0.1–0.5 mm grains.

As in samples No. 1, 5, and 6, the white base consists of clear glass mixed with gypsum and quartz grains.

The top coating is white. The glass is clean, dense, and homogeneous, with rare air bubbles closer to the base.

Green fragment (No. 6). The colored layer is 0.5 mm thick. The white base and the green glass layer are 0.2 mm each, featured with about 0.1 mm of the thin layer of pure glass with iridescent effect (iridization) at the sample's top. This top layer is dense and transparent, it breaks off from the green glass easily, forming plates of different sizes. Thus, the green fragments have three layers of substance applied to the base in contrast to all other that have only two. This may be due to the lower resistance of the green pigment to surface conditions.

The green layer consists of almost pure glass, strongly fractured with inclusions of quartz grains. Green glass is more transparent and homogeneous than the others. It almost does not have air bubbles. Glass breaks into irregularly shaped large pieces (up to 5 mm) when crushed.

When physically exposed, the white substrate breaks down uniformly to its natural grain size – mostly up to 1 mm, with a minimum grain size of 0.1 mm.

The back and base of the tile contains quartz grains measuring 0.1–0.5 mm. Glass pieces are slightly melted, and the substrate contains sharp-angled fragments. Feldspar is represented by weakly calcined grains.

Yellow fragment (No. 4). The colored layer is 0.3–0.5 mm thick. The upper part is no more than 0.1 mm. The yellow substance is a porous mass with a matte surface and rare inclusions of quartz. Paint residues

have smears in cracks, and the paint dust is scattered in the total mass of the sample. This substance is applied to a bluish-white substrate, mostly made of quartz. This substrate is scratched, probably to improve the fixation of the pigment layer.

The substrate pieces are most often up to 2 mm, very rarely up to 5 mm. The rest is as in other samples.

Red fragment (No. 7). The color layer is 0.3 mm thick. The white substrate is 0.2 mm thick, not more than 0.1 mm is covered with a porous mass with a matte surface and rare quartz inclusions, similar to that on the yellow sample. The surface has cracks filled with quartz (probably formed when the tiles were heated). The quartz that fills the cracks forms convex surfaces that trace the cracks.

The substrate is represented by a white mass, similar to that in the substrate of the yellow fragments. The paint has been applied on top of this mass. The painted tiles have been heated. It is indicated by a thin layer of clear, dense, and transparent glass on the lower surface of the colored coating, meaning that the paint was 'welded'. The rest is the same as in the other samples.

We can distinguish three variants of tile production testifying to the multi-stage process. The base of all the Kinski Vody tiles is the same, possibly made from local alluvial river sediments. Ground gypsum was added to the mass for better binding, which sometimes crystallized during heating.

Seemingly identical sediments were also used to create substrates. However, there were two different variants of those substrates. One variant was used for white, blue, turquoise and green fragments. It is less dense and has larger grains. The other variant was used to make yellow and red mosaic. The latter required a denser substrate for cementing the coloured layer. This second method was necessary as the yellow and red coloured layer does not contain quartz material; it features only the pigment. Green fragments, additionally, are covered with a thin layer of quartz glass which protect the pigment.

Apparently, the process included a multistage heat treatment (firing) at different temperatures. The first stage involved— making the base and firing. In the second, the base was covered with the substrate and fired (depending on the composition and the required resulting density of the substrate, different temperatures were used). Thirdly, the substrate was covered with the pigment layer and fired (also at different temperatures because yellow fragments do not have a fused base paint, while there is some of it in red ones). The fourth step involved only green fragments and included adding the glass layer before a final firing.

Photoluminescence

The photoluminescence study revealed that samples form two different groups. First includes those, where the colored layer is characterized by a luminescence similar to the one of quartz glass — individual dots of blue color on the general dark background. These are tiles with white, turquoise, or blue layers.

Samples from the second group (with yellow, red, or green layers) return brown luminescence. Yellow samples are slightly lighter than red ones. The green ones are luminescent in same way as the red ones — with dark brown light, — but the intensity is less. Such luminescence of the samples of the second group is explainable by the presence of lead ochre in the pigments.

Two groups of photoluminescence support the idea that different methods of adding and cementing the pigment layer depend on the pigment composition.

X-ray spectroscopy was carried out in the spectral laboratory of the Crimean Branch of UkrSGEI for 41 elements by Galina Rein, a chemical engineer.

The chromophore elements and characteristic admixtures (Cu, Pb, Sn, Ag, Sb, Co, Ba, P, As, Hg) are described below. In addition, Ni, Zn, Mo, Cr, V, Ti, Mg, Mn, Nb, Zr, Ga, La, Bi, Li, Tl, B, Al, Fe, Ca, Si, and Na have been measured. Relatively high content of sodium (0.8–12 %) can be explained by its inclusion in the composition of soda, historically used for glassmaking. Silicon, aluminum, magnesium, and calcium are the main constituents of glass and substrate. Other elements are represented by admixtures in minerals (quartz, clay, feldspar, magnetite, etc.).

Be, Ce, Y, Yb, W, Ge, Sc, Sr, Cd, Au are not detected. Some results returned too much Sr, which does not allow for determining lithium's presence or absence (Li). There is much more Si than indicated, as determined by semi-quantitative analysis. These results allowed to draw some conclusions on the nature of pigments and initial raw materials for glaze. According to the content of critical elements-chromophores and characteristic impurities, the fragments (samples) can be grouped as follows:

1. Fragments 2 and 3 (base and white tile). There is no high content of elements-chromophores. The obtained parameters correspond to the composition of quartz-clay mixture as described by microscopic study.

2. Fragments 1, 1a, and 6 (turquoise (bright and light) and green). Chromophore elements are copper (1.5 % in 1 and 1a; 1.2 % – in 6), lead (0.5 % and 12 %, respectively), tin (0.32 % and 2.5 %), silver (only in 6 – 0.08 %), antimony (only in 6 – 3.2 %). The high content of copper (probably sulfate), lead (ochre), and tin is characteristic of these fragments. Obviously, changing the ratio of these components changes the color of the glaze: Sn/Pb/Cu = 1/1.56/4.69 (turquoise color), Sn/Pb/Cu = 1/4.8/0.48 (green). The addition of lead to copper-based dye gives it a blue tint. A high silver content has also been found for the green coloring, resulting in a possibly higher transparency of the glass.

3. Fragments 4 and 7 (yellow and red) are characterized by high lead content without increased copper content (6.3 % and 0.5 % respectively). In the red fragment, only lead admixtures are responsible for coloring, while in the yellow one, tin (8.0 %), silver (0.002 %), and antimony (1.0 %) are presented in recognizable quantity.

4. Fragments 5 and 5a (blue). This group is characterized by the increased content of elements not established in other glaze types – cobalt (blue chromophore, 0.12 %), barium (0.04 %), phosphorus (0.8 %), arsenic (0.2 %), mercury (0.0063 %). Other composition of admixtures allows to assume another type of initial raw material for this glaze, i. e. a different kind of ores being used to obtain the paint (glaze).

Results indicate that cobalt (samples 5 and 5a) was brought in from other places. Its non-typical high barium, phosphorus, arsenic and mercury content indicates a different type of deposit (formation of cobalt-bearing ores) and possibly a different mining area. The raw material of the mineral for paint (pigment for glazes) in samples 1, 1a, 4, 6, and 7 was likely polymetallic lead-tin ores. We know this as their oxidized parts often come to the surface of the glaze, where ore minerals undergo secondary transformations.

Interpretation and hypotheses

To compare these results with those from similar studies, I tried to find sources where similar methods were applied to the Kashi mosaic or similar fragments to those from Kinski Vody are described. It turned out to be not that simple: all researchers use different sets of situationally available methods, and there is no unified set or protocol. However, some parallels can be traced. For example, the results obtained from Kinski Vody align well with the results of quantitative (X-ray) spectral analysis, provided by Koval (Koval 2010) for “semifaience” turquoise glazes without additional decoration, %: Na₂O – 14–14.2; K₂O – 1.5–1.6; CaO – 4.4–4.6; SnO₂ > 0.1; PbO – 2.8–3.3; Sb₂O₃ – > 0.1; MgO > 2–2.3; Al₂O₃ – 1.2–1.6; MnO > 0.1; FeO – 0.5; CuO – 0.5–0.6; CoO – 0; SiO₂ – 70–71; Ti > 0.1.

The classification and chronology for the glazed ceramics from Central Asia, including architectural materials, was carried out by Shyshkina (Shyshkina 1979). She used technological features to be the primary classification parameters. Starting from separating the building tiles as a distinctive set of artifacts, Shyshkina classified glazes and manufacturing techniques based on the manufacture period and the location of the production center. She also noticed that the composition of “architectural” and “tableware” glazes is practically indistinguishable and separated faience (kashi) without slipware and with white slipware from other groups. In terms of the quality of the glaze coating, Shyshkina distinguished opaque and transparent alkaline-lead-tin glaze.

Due to the similarity of the “architectural” and “tableware” glazes, Shyshkina considers tiles as a separate group only functionally. She indicates that “around the middle of the XIII century, as the of faience (Kashi) ware spread around, potters used two types of blue (turquoise) glaze: opaque – to apply to the loess-clay base and transparent – for faience. The composition of the former differed little from the early translucent alkaline-lead-tin glazes, while the latter was probably “alkaline.” Shyshkina also indicated that according to the Institute of History and Archaeology of the Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek Soviet Socialist Republic, the melting temperature of transparent glazes of the second half of the IX–X centuries did not exceed 750 °C. The comparison of our data and those collected by Shyshkina (1979) is shown in Table 2.

The chemical composition of glazes of the group 1 and 2 from Basra, provided by Shyshkina (1979), is as follows, %: Na₂O – 7.4–11.2; K₂O – 4.1–4.9; CaO – 4.8–6.7; SnO₂ – <5.6; PbO – 1.1–1.9; MgO – 1.7–3.7; Al₂O₃ – 0.6–2.1; FeO – 0.5–1.0; SiO₂ – 67.6–73.9. No results are given about the content of Sb₂O₃, MnO, CuO, CoO, Ti. Though Elnikov (2017) indicates less sodium and more potassium, the sum of these alkalis is the same.

The glaze itself contains around 10 % of rounded quartz grains, around 2 % of feldspar, and less than 1 % of plagioclase. The rest is glass. The size of mineral grains is 0.1–0.8 mm, and the degree of roundness varies from 0.2 to 0.9 (i. e. from partially chipped to practically round). Microphotographs of the monotonous turquoise glaze published by Koval (2010) present the grains of rare dark-colored minerals in the glassy mass (with predominant size up to 0.0125 mm) and larger melted quartz grains. Both composition and description practically correspond to the results obtained from Kinsky Vody. This seems reasonable given the historical pieces of evidence on mining and production of dyes in the region, including those possibly used for kashi mosaic.

Glazed elements were introduced into architectural decor not earlier than the second half of the XI century. At first, they were made of clay mass and shaped rectangular tiles with white, blue (turquoise), and violet (possibly dark blue and cobalt, similar in color to lapis lazuli) glaze. At the same time, alkaline

lead-tin glazes (with firing temperatures around 860 °C) are characteristic of the artifacts from Samarkand.

From the second half of the 11th century, the appearance of cobalt dye in architectural decoration glazes is clearly recorded, including in Afrasiab, the ancient Sogdian capital, the legendary Marakanda (present-day Samarkand), where during the 11th century the extension and repair of the Shakh-i-Zinda mosque, glazed blue bricks with beveled long lateral planes (similar to those found at the Kinski Vody settlement) were used to decorate the mihrab's wall. During the excavations of the citadel of Afrasiab, numerous uni- and bi-coloured bricks, as well as unicoloured rectangular, star-shaped, trapezoidal and triangular tiles were discovered together with the ornamental fragments similar to those found at Kinski Vody. Unicolour glazes on faience (kashi) were the most common ones in Sogd in the 8th – early 14th centuries. See Figures 4-5.

Figure 4. Shakh-i-Zinda, 11th-15th century. Samarkand, Uzbekistan Image by Bobyrr, licensed with CC BY-SA-4.0. Retrieved on 31.04.2024 by the [link](#).

Many analyses of mineral and chemical composition, granulometric studies, and technological descriptions are given in Robert's Mason book *Shine Like the Sun* (Mason 2004). Mason analyzes and describes in detail the ware glazes of Iraq, Iran, Egypt, and Syria from approximately the late VIII to early XVI centuries. This is the most complete, detailed, and up-to-date study available at the time of research. Iran, unfortunately, is described mostly by late (XV century) sites, with earlier descriptions only of luster or multicolored ware. The glazes from Egypt and Syria have an unambiguously different composition than those of Iran and Iraq. The latter are similar to those found in Ukraine, while the former ones used different raw materials. This is evident, of course, by the composition of pigments having a different ratio of components and composition of impurities, not by the clay or the quartz sand.

Figure 5. Namozgoh mosque, 17th century. Samarkand, Uzbekistan. A — general view; B — close-up of the mosaic. Images by Image by Olena Vakarenko, used here with permission.

The results obtained from Kinski Vody allowed correlating them with known pigments published by Mason (2004) (Table 3).

Not going into details of all Mason's analyses, I only mention briefly those that I found interesting and useful for the study. For example, the classification of alkaline lead-tin glazes by the ratio of lead and tin oxide content values based on the results of microprobe analysis clearly illustrates differences in the origin of glazes of the Iranian Plateau and Egypt. Based on the results of spectral analysis by Koval (2010), the composition of the turquoise glaze corresponds to those from Basra, and the glaze found at Kinski Vody, in turn, is similar to it.

Unlike Shyshkina, Mason aims to classify fragments of tableware and architectural ceramics based on their purpose. He describes these objects and their parts in detail, while chemistry and technology play an auxiliary role. In Mason's typology, ornamented ware takes groups 1 and 2. The ware is attributed to the VIII and IX centuries; it is the basic monochrome turquoise glaze. The decorated artifacts emerge later, same as chandeliers, and multicolor ones. The ratio of components in the glaze becomes different, but the initial raw material remains the same. Group 3 of glazes from Basra is similar to those from Kinski Vody (see Table 3). This glaze has less SiO₂ and more metals. However, as Mason primarily looks at a tableware glaze, its colored layer is thinner than for the architectural glaze, and the data require additional confirmation. It also requires more uniformity and less granularity. "Ordinary" glazes of Kashan also look like those from Basra and Kinski Vody.

At first glance, comparing the glazes of Sogd and Basra seems unproductive. The fact that Shishkina worked with mainly Soviet collections and Mason studied Western ones also imposes some limitations. The only point of intersection between them is the collection of the Bohdan and Varvara Khanenko Museum (Kyiv, Ukraine), but both sources don't describe those samples from this museum that might be of interest to this study. Fragmentary and scattered data, significantly different research time, and

different methods and laboratories applied make attempts to connect and compare the data barely productive. However, the geological data indicate that some interpolation is reasonable.

Sogd, Kashan, and Basra are located within the same geological structure – in the Kopet Dag, Zagros, and Elbrus regions. All this territory is characterized by a wide development of deposits coming into the open air. One of the most famous deposits is called Almalyk – the red top – where ore mining locations have been known from III-II century BCE and continue to this day. It is the largest metallurgical center of Uzbekistan, located on the slopes of the Qurama Mountains near the Angren River. Many deposits rich with copper minerals (often represented by cuprous, blue-green copper sulfate compounds) are located here. They are loose, easy to process, and mostly oxidized on the surface. Deeper mining might provide sulfides with bright multicolored secondary minerals, also easy to extract and process, that serve as a ready-made raw material for a variety of dyes. All of these formations are characterized by an almost complete absence of iron and increased content of tin and silver. The characteristic minerals of such deposits are malachite, azurite, brochantite, cuprite, tenorite, nugget copper, gold, and small amounts of sulfides (chalcocite, chalcopyrite). The formation also has complexes of phosphate and silicate copper compounds – chrysocolla, pseudomalachite, libethenite, turquoise, elite, cuprous halloysite, mixtures of kaolinite with chrysocolla, amorphous formations of malachite. Rocks composed of quartzites, skarns (contact rocks at the boundary of magmatic rocks intrusion into clay sedimentary rocks), quartz sandstones, and less often clayey rocks. They probably served as a basis for Kashi and slipware and possibly as a filler or admixture for dyes.

It is worth noticing that all (!) deposits and ore occurrences active today were discovered and described here according to archaeological data. There are thousand-year-old mines from the VIII–XIV centuries, with the most active mining period dating back to the X–XI centuries. For example, the Jezkazgan copper deposit (the second largest in the world) is located in this area. Many polymetal deposits and rich lead ores are known in the Karatau Mountains (South Kazakhstan). There is written evidence that back in the times of the Dzungars and Tamerlane, copper, silver, and lead were mined in these areas, and these metals were used in the construction of mosques, including the famous Turkestan Mausoleum of Khoja Ahmed Yasawi. See fig. 6.

Figure 6. The decorated walls of the Mausoleum of Khawaja Ahmed Yasawi, 14th century. Turkestan, Kazakhstan. Image by Davide Mauro, licensed with CC BY-SA-4.0. Retrieved at 15.06.2024 by the [link](#).

Mason indicates the same territories as sources of raw materials for Basra and Sogd glazes. He describes similar geological facts and uses the same toponyms, mentioning Almalyk and similar deposits of polymetals that developed during the reigns of Malik Shah and Sultan Muhammad.

Discussion

The chemical and mineralogical study outlined above offers some insights into the chain of glaze production. The Iranian Plateau as well as the vast territories of modern Uzbekistan, Tajikistan and Turkmenistan (Buryakov 1974) was home to ore mining. It seems that the production of pigments as dry mineral-based powder mixtures was also confined to the mining locations. In its time of prosperity (late 11th to early 13th centuries), the Great Seljuk Empire--which included almost all of Iran and Iraq--captured Samarkand, Fergana and Bukhara and began the active construction of roads, caravanserais, madrasas and mosques. At the same time, the development of large mining deposits became more active, and the need for well-functioning trade routes for transportation increased.

As long as the Eurasian Steppe was divided between different nomadic groups, all caravans along the route were liable to be attacked and robbed. By paying different nomadic groups for the right to pass through their territory, and sometimes for temporary lodging, merchants found some measure of security along the route.

Khazanov (2022) believes that trade along the numerous fragmented Silk Road routes should be studied using a network approach. The changing nodes of a trade route network connected specific traders linked directly to several such places in regional networks. Regional traders provided the bulk of the movement of goods via small caravans, while cities were transshipment points: some of the goods were sold locally, and some were delivered elsewhere by other merchants (the distance from Samarkand to the Mediterranean Sea is about 3000 km). These cities were transshipment points: some of the goods were sold locally, and some were delivered by other merchants. In other words, trade was segmented and each commodity passed through many hands from the place of its production to the final consumer.

Traveling as part of a large caravan of hundreds of traders was safer, but it was less frequent, took more time, and cost considerably more, making the goods more expensive.

Long-distance trade flourished in the 13th century during the Mongol Empire, whose rulers, starting with Genghis Khan, tried to develop and support international trade and secure trade routes and foreign merchants. For example, merchants were allowed to use the Mongolian postal system (Yam), created for messengers and major officials. It was a time of a significant unification of many trade routes – the closest thing to our modern idea of the Silk Road as a trade highway. The Road carried not only silk and other status items from East to West but also transferred religions, languages, crafts and craftsmen, scientific knowledge and technology, inventions, fashion and cuisine, metals, chemicals, minerals, plants, diseases, and medicine (Khazanov 2022).

But even in these times of relative security and revitalization, the ratio of goods' value to volume was extremely important, and intermediaries and transshipment hubs (nodes of the network) did not lose their role. Such complex systems involved many people - merchants, guards, traders, interpreters and guides – who could function only through mutual trust. However, cases of fraud are also known and

described in both scientific literature as well as works of fiction. If caught, the fate of a thief or fraudster was unenviable. There was no third option; those who wanted to trade and travel, trusted. Those who did not want to be punished, did not cheat or steal more than could be forgiven.

Thus, the mineral pigments extracted from the Iranian Plateau were crushed, abraded, mixed with aggregates and binders and sold. In the form of dry mixtures, they were transported to ceramic production places. Therefore, the chemical composition of the glaze of building and tableware ceramics along the Silk Road was be identical while the technology of pigments, various additives, firing temperatures and the bases upon which the glaze was applied differed. In places where glazed wares were produced, glaze bases and substrates were made from local raw materials, which obviously caused some technological peculiarities.

In Samarkand, for example, the turquoise glaze is applied directly to building ceramics without creating a substrate (slipware). The base of ceramics here is predominantly made of clay – dense and massive. Perhaps, the glaze there was cheaper or of better quality (or maybe both), as the production was located closer to the source of raw materials. Besides, the territory of Afrasiab is loess hills, where rather dense clays are widespread. They served as a basis for local architectural ceramics. It is possible that glaze could be applied on such a dense fine-grained base without a substrate — the necessary quality was preserved. Interestingly, today tour guides and historians in Samarkand claim that the old glazed elements are preserved and look better than those made in recent decades for the restoration of monuments: all new and restored fall apart after the first or second winter, the glaze starts to crack, peel off and crumble. The secrets of old compositions and technologies of “eternal” turquoise glaze could not be restored now.

In Ukraine, where sediments are looser, the base of mosaics fragments is loose and crumbly and made of sandy gypsum with an admixture of clay material. Therefore, the glaze would be less stable and durable. So before applying expensive imported dyes that arrived from the Iranian Plateau along the Silk Road, these fragments were covered with a white substrate of finely crushed quartz-gypsum mixture. Possibly, the slipware from local raw allowed to reduce the consumption of pigment and apply a thinner layer of paint. The bricks from Samarkand and Basra are much denser and more homogeneous than the clay base from Kinski Vody and were burnt at a higher temperature, so the layer of bright turquoise watering on them was relatively uniform.

When taking into account the peculiarities of pigments applied to them, the multistage technology of mosaic tile production leads to two important ideas: 1) in Ukraine, the construction of Muslim cities was performed by experienced and skillful craftsmen, who understood the peculiarities of working with different substances well; 2) these craftsmen tried to ensure the maximum quality of the products they used, which would satisfy the customer and also use as little expensive imported raw materials as possible. By complicating the technology (i.e. by introducing additional operations, such as scratching and baking the base and applying a protective layer of luster), masters tried to ensure the durability of the paint and the economic profitability of the process. It is obvious that the complication and increase in labor inputs discovered in this study did not lead to a significant increase in cost. Raw materials were more expensive than the additional labor spent to save them.

Since the glazes studied in Ukraine and Central Asia differ in the amount of quartz and gypsum, it can also be assumed that the pigments mined on the Iranian Plateau were diluted in many locations: at resale points and at the locations of glaze production. They were sold by weight, so the sellers added quartz sand to the pigment bags, which they could not, did not have time to, or did not try hard enough to grind.

The key factors of this trade were time, trust and economic expediency. Both the seller, the intermediary, and the client were trying to get their own profit, but did not want to lose trust and trade relations, i. e. their reputation. Therefore, none of them allowed actions that would significantly deteriorate the quality of goods. Such a concern for reputation is indirectly confirmed by the fact that the more expensive, fine and difficult-to-use red, yellow, green and blue pigments were not diluted, unlike turquoise, the cheapest and most common pigment. See Figure 7.

Figure 7. Gradual change in the 14th-century mosaic colour from west (left) to east (right). A — Kinsky Vody; B — Bukhara (Masjidi Kalon); C — Samarkand; D — Turkestan. 1 — Images by Anna Radchenko; 2 — Image by Adam Jones, licensed with CC BY-SA-4.0; 3 — Image by Bobyrr, licensed with CC BY-SA-4.0; 4 — Image by Davide Mauro, licensed with CC BY-SA-4.0.

The line between conscious and inevitable fraud and serious deception was thin and well-understood by the participants. So, trust became part of the economic model and an integral characteristic of the Silk Road. As the number of hands the dyes were going through on their way to the West grew, the higher the risk of their modification. In our case – it was mixing of dry dyes with quartz powder. Therefore, the closer to the place of extraction of mineral components of paints (Iranian highlands), the denser, more homogeneous, and brighter were glazes. By the way, literary sources do not mention small grains of quartz and shards present in the watering, but our study of Ukrainian artifacts revealed their presence. Besides, a fragment of tile obtained from Samarkand showed not only a thicker but also a denser and more homogeneous layer of turquoise pigment applied without slipware. Therefore, the trade rule for building mixtures confirms that the farther from the place of extraction, the higher the price, the more resellers, and the worse the goods. Overall, this rule can be confirmed by the archaeological data, through a study of construction ceramics with a set of unified mineralogical methods. In this way, one could quantify the “degree of trust” as an economic component, showing the gradual dilution of dry mineral pigments.

It is possible that the dyes were also mixed and diluted at the last station, where the goods were about to be used. For example, local craftsmen could dilute expensive pigments, saving them for later. This allowed to reduce the production costs, and, apparently, suited the customers: transporting building tiles was prohibitively expensive. And the customers might not have known what the celestial turquoise should actually look like.

Conclusion

This text presents the most complete study of the glazes of architectural ceramics of the XIV century in Ukraine carried out with analytical methods. The composition of the base of mosaic tiles does not allow to draw conclusions about its origin — it is almost pure alluvial quartz sand. Some indirect signs suggest that the raw materials used for the base were local. The probability of local production is also confirmed

by the findings of ceramic “pins” at the Kinski Vody settlement (Radchenko 2017). These pins were probably used during the firing of Kashi mosaic. Elnikov also refers to the possibility of the local production of pottery and mosaics based on the evidence from the early XX century written sources that described the possible leftovers of the manufacturing locations (Elnikov 2017; Radchenko 2017).

The raw materials used for the production of glazes were not local. The composition of the studied glaze and available archaeological and geological data indicate that the raw materials could have been mined in the Iranian Plateau and adjacent lands – from Samarkand to Basra. All this territory is characterized by similar geological formations with similar polymetallic deposits known at least since the VIII century. These raw materials came to Ukraine through a part of the Great Silk Road network, whose importance increased again in the XIII century due to the flourishing of the Mongol Empire, when the trade was conducted mainly by Muslims (Khazanov 2022). The available data on the composition of the ware glaze allow us to assume the use of the common raw materials for its production in this territory, as the compositions described by different researchers testify to technological differences rather than material ones. Technological differences seem to be caused not only by technological rationality, but also by the economic one — that is, technology depends on economic relations in the network of traders, their benefits, trust, and conventions between them.

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Table 1: Characteristics of fragments and their mineral composition, %

Component	Sample number and description (top layer color)								
	1	1a	2	3	4	5	5a	6	7
	Bright turquoise	Light turquoise	Mosaic base	White	Yellow	Blue (light)	Blue (dark)	Green	Red
Quartz	10—15	15—20	30	15	15	15	15	30	15
Glass (top part of the colored layer)	15	15	—	15	—	15—20	20—25	20	— (paint, pieces up to 15 %)
White glass*	35—40	35—40	20	30	20	60—65	55—60	up to 40	60—65
Gypsum	30	25	50	30	30	3—5	3—5	10	3—5
Iron hydroxides	1—2	Sgl. gr.	Sgl. gr.	Sgl. gr.		1—2	1—2	1	—
Potassium feldspar	Sgl. gr.	Sgl. gr.	Sgl. gr.	up to 1	up to 1	Sgl. gr.	Sgl. gr.	—	Sgl. gr.
Magnetite	—	—	Sgl. gr.	Sgl. gr.	Sgl. gr.	—	—	Sgl. gr.	—

* — substrate and material dispersed in the base mass

Note. Present in all samples gypsum, magnetite and fossilized quartz grains, obviously, represent the material of the base of tiles – quartz river alluvial sand mixed with crushed to pulverized gypsum. Carbonate material is absent. Sgl. gr. — single grains. All samples contain pieces of gray metal — modern contamination associated with sample preparation. Sample. No. 5 is blue, colored intensely, in color similar to lazurite. In sample No. 6 fragments of the upper layer — thin plates of iridescent glass — 1—2 % were found. Sample No. 4 would have as much coloring as in No. 7, but we had to remove it and use it for other analytical studies (not enough material).

Table 2: Content of some elements in turquoise, white and green glaze (results of spectral analysis, according to different sources), %

Element	Source, glaze color							
	Our data			after Shishkina 1979				
	Turquoise	White	Green	Turquoise, Samarkand, XII—XIII c. (I.O.Ng)*		White, Samarkand, IX c., "ishkor" glaze (I.O.N.A)*		Green, Afrasiab (I.O.RA.gd)
Cu	1,5	0,005	1,2	0,3	3,0	0,3	> 2	0,3
Pb	0,5	0,032	12,0	1,0	20,0	> 1	3,0	> 1
Co	0,0008	0,0004	0,001	0,001	—	0,001	—	0,003
Ni	0,0012	0,0005	0,0012	0,001	—	0,001	—	0,001
Zn	0,004	0,005	0,0032	0,001	—	—	—	0,03
Mo	0,0002	0,0002	0,0005			—	—	0,001
Cr	0,0008	0,001	0,0012	0,003	—	0,03	—	0,006
V	0,0015	0,002	0,0063	0,006	—	0,003	1,0	0,003
Ti	0,04	0,063	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,06	2,0	0,3
Sn	0,32	0,008	2,5	0,3	2,0	> 1	2,0	~ 1
Mg	4,0	2,5	2,0	1,0	5,0	> 1	4,0	> 1
Mn	0,015	0,02	0,015	0,01	tr.	0,01	3,0	1,06
Ba	—	—	—	0,01	—	0,03	tr.	0,03
Nb	—	—	—					
Zr	—	0,0032	0,005	0,006	—	0,003	1,0	0,006
Ga	0,0004	0,0005	0,0004	0,001	—	0,001	1,0	0,001
La	0,001	0,0012	—			0,001	1,0	
Ag	0,0002	0,00008	0,008	0,003	tr.			0,006
Bi	0,0005	—	0,0004	0,01	—	—	—	0,01
Li	0,002	0,0015	Sb					—
P	0,1	0,1	0,5	0,01	—	—	—	0,3
As	0,01	—	0,063					0,01
Sb	0,015	—	3,2	—	—	—	—	0,03
Hg	—	—	—					
Tl	0,00012	—	0,00012					
B	0,0080	0,01	0,008					
Al	0,63	0,8	1,0	1,0	0,3	> 1	5,0	> 1
Fe	0,5	0,8	0,8	0,6	1,5	> 1	4,0	> 1
Ca	3,2	2,5	2,5	1,0	4,0	> 1	4,0	> 1
Si	25,0	25,0	25,0	1,0	bs.	> 1	5,0	> 1
Na	1,5	12,0	8,0	1,0	5,0	> 1	5,0	> 1

Note. Shishkina points out that the analyses were made in different laboratories; I.O.Ng — Samarkand blue opaque alkaline-lead-tin glaze; loess-clay shard without engobe, XII—XIII cc.; I.O.N.A — white opaque alkaline-lead-tin glaze; loess-clay shard without engobe; I.O.RA.gd — early transparent and translucent alkaline-lead-tin glazes; loess-clay shard without engobe; tr. — traces (present, but impossible to measure how much); bs. — basic (so much that it is difficult to estimate the quantity). Empty cells mean the absence of data.

Table 3: Composition, some chemical and thermal properties of used pigments (Mason 2004)

Pigment name	Chemical composition	Tempering, up to 1000 °C		Interaction with HNO ₃ or HCl	Beginning of the use
		T, °C	Type of transformation and color change over time		
White pigments					
Lead paint	2PbCO ₃ · Pb(OH) ₂	600	2PbCO ₃ → Pb(OH) ₂ → PbO turns yellow	dissolves with rapid release of CO ₂ , in solution Pb ²⁺	Since the ancient classics
Blue pigments					
Azurite	2CuCO ₃ · Cu(OH) ₂	300 — 500	Azurite → tenorite CuO, blackening	dissolves with rapid release of CO ₂ , in solution Cu ²⁺	Since the ancient classics. Artificial azurite has been found in works since the 17 th century.
Red pigments					
Minimum	Pb ₃ O ₄	>600	Pb ₃ O ₄ → PbO (massicot), turns yellow	dissolves, after cooling a white precipitate of PbCl ₂	Since the ancient classics
Green pigments					
Malachite	CuCO ₃ · Cu(OH) ₂	280 — 420	Malachite → tenorite CuO, blackening	dissolves with violent release of CO ₂ , in Cu ²⁺ solution	Since the ancient classics. Artificial malachite has been found in the 14 th century. manuscript.
Yellow pigments					
Massicot	PbO	800 — 900	Melting does not change	dissolves, after cooling a precipitate of white PbCl ₂	Known before our era, but used only in later times
Lead-tin yellow. (type I)	Pb ₂ SnO ₄	900	Pb ₂ SnO ₄ → SnO ₂ + PbO does not change	soluble, in solution Pb ²⁺ , Sn(IV)	Encountered in painting at the turn of the 13 th —14 th , was widely used until the beginning of the 18 th century.